

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DAINKEH****FIRST NAME: ATUMANNI****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago footnote (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 2%

The author uses MSWord 2013 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **A critical aspect of writing a research paper is building and organizing the researcher's argument. In Turabian's book, five elements that a researcher must consider on his reader's behalf to make a sound research argument are:**

- Research question, hypothesis, methodology, findings, and discussion.
- Response, claim, hypothesis, evidence, discussion.
- Claim, reason, evidence, acknowledgment response, and warrant.¹**
- Purpose of study, warrant, research question, hypothesis, findings.

¹ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*: Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing. Ninth edition (Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 58.

2. **The fundamental difference between the qualitative and quantitative research paradigms is:**

- An understanding of the nature of reality and the concept of the existence of bias in research.²**
- The qualitative paradigm only uses interviews as a data collection method, whilst the quantitative paradigm only uses surveys for collecting data.
- Sampling in qualitative research is always purposive, whereas sampling in quantitative research is always randomized.
- Research findings in qualitative research cannot be generalized, whereas findings in quantitative research are always generalizable.

3. **What is plagiarism?**

- An academic offense in which a writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.³**
- An unethical academic conduct.
- A failure to use the appropriate punctuation marks in writing.
- Using both Standard British English and Standard American English in the same essay.

² James P. Sampson. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second edition (Florida: Florida State University, 2017), 34.

³ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

4. **In addition to preventing the offense of plagiarism, appropriate citation, according to Turabian's book, serves the following purposes:**
- Increases the chance of getting your work published in reputable journals.
 - It is what readers like to see most in scholarly work.
 - Gives scholarly work a logical and comprehensive outlook.
 - Enhances the integrity of your work, strengthens your argument as well as giving credit to the originality of the information.⁴**
5. **The term 'research' is frequently used in many contexts by both academics and non-academics. Which of the following that best defines what it is?**
- A thorough and meticulous investigation that aims at making a discovery or solving a query.
 - The process of carefully collecting data to prove a hypothesis.
 - A process of systematic inquiry to answer a question that not only the researcher but others want to solve, and such systematic inquiry does not only need to advance the body of knowledge of the subject matter under investigation for the benefit of the public but also advances or crystallizes the researcher's knowledge of the subject matter being investigated.⁵**
 - A method of inquisition that can only be successfully undertaken by an academic.
6. **In writing a scholarly essay, the most important things to have in mind are:**

⁴ Turabian et al., 139.

⁵ Ibid., 19.

Starting the central thesis of the essay from the outset, staying focused on the subject matter under discussion, clarity of writing with short, unambiguous sentences, and avoiding plagiarism.⁶

Sticking to the deadline for submission of the essay.

Maintaining a rule of style.

Non-reliance on a word processor spell-checker.

7. **Writing an academic essay consists of numerous steps that are not rigidly linear and there are certain steps that must be undertaken before starting the write-up.**

These are:

Beating procrastination and starting early, which includes researching the topic by reading extensively to gain a clearer understanding and evidence to develop your thesis.⁷

Drafting a plan on how to go about the essay.

Seeking the views of as many people as possible on the subject matter.

Familiarize yourself with Zotero software before starting to write.

8. **In writing a dissertation research paper, four main components must be adhered to, namely:**

⁶ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 13.

⁷ Ibid., 8.

The concept paper, the dissertation prospectus, the dissertation, and the dissertation manuscript.⁸

Introduction, methodology, findings, and discussion.

Abstract, introduction, findings, and discussion.

Introduction, research design, conceptual framework, and findings.

9. **The qualitative research approach predicates itself on the principles of:**

Transparency, credibility, and coherence.⁹

Transparency, reliability, and generalizability.

Credibility, coherence, and validity.

Objectivity, trustworthiness, and coherence.

10. **At Euclid University, the recommended rule of style is the Chicago (Turabian) rule of style. A key advantage of using a rule of style in scholarly writing is that:**

It helps to maintain consistency in writing, thereby saving time in proofreading and correction.¹⁰

It reduces the risk of plagiarism.

It allows the use of the first person singular.

It attracts and retains readers' attention to the piece of scholarly work.

⁸ Sampson, 2.

⁹ Ibid., 37.

¹⁰ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 41.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.